

QUIZ

LAST NAME: BOTON
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PROGRAM CODE: DDIA
COURSE CODE: ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 6
INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes).
The author did use Zotero to insert references.
The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. According to the Turabian rule of style, there are two categories of online sources the common feature of which is the medium. No matter which one of those sources you cite in those two categories, you must:**
 - Include standards facts of publication such as author's name, title, date and so forth.
 - Include standard facts and URL.
 - Include author's name, title, URL and date accessed.
 - Include the full fact of publication in addition to a URL.¹**

- 2. The dissertation defense ritual is for the Ph.D. student:**
 - An opportunity to fight fiercely for his/her claims and statements before the defense committee.

Commented [GK1]: All the options are not to be capitalized. Kindly undo all

¹ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.*, ed. University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff Wayne Booth, Gregory Colomb, Joseph Williams, 8th ed., (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 188.

- An opportunity to publicly present his/her research and in a proactive, but non-defensive manner.²**
- An opportunity to defend their thesis and show the document is perfect in every point.
- An opportunity to defensively demonstrate to the public and the defense committee the truthfulness of the results they have arrived at.
3. **Most Ph.D. students who have chronic procrastination habits usually feel intimidated by their project that they are not able to start writing their dissertation. In such a case, what should a student do to overcome the situation?**
- The student should keep on reading more materials.
- The student should start a section, stick to it even if he/she gets blocked and ensure to complete it before he/she move to another section.
- The student should break the project into small, achievable goals.³**
- Contemplate narrowing down the scope of the work.
4. **According to Bloomberg and Volpe, the information included in an abstract influences whether or not the reader should proceed to read the total study. The authors then suggest that the content of an abstract should typically include the following elements:**
- Title of study, key findings, conclusions and recommendations, research problem or issue addressed, qualitative research tradition or genre, theoretical basis that guided the study, data sources that informed the study, names of research supervisors.
- Name of institution, key findings, conclusions and recommendations, research problem or issue addressed, qualitative research tradition or genre, theoretical basis that guided the study,

Commented [GK2]: Since you are using US English, observe the US punctuation for abbreviations like this. Kindly review the entire paper and effect changes across board

² Bloomberg, Linda D. and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 173

³ Turabian, 48.

date of completion, methods and procedures of data collection and data analysis.

Title of study, key findings, conclusions and recommendations, research problem or issue addressed, qualitative research tradition or genre, theoretical basis that guided the study, data sources that informed the study, methods and procedures of data collection and data analysis.⁴

Area of study, key findings, acknowledgment, research problem or issue addressed, qualitative research tradition or genre, religious orientation of researcher, data sources that informed the study, methods and procedures of data collection and data analysis.

5. **According to the Turabian rule of styles, the facts of publication of a work usually include three elements that are the place of publication, the name of the publisher and the date of publication. What are the components of the date of publication?**

The publication date for a book consists of the year, the month and day the book was published.

The publication date for a book consists of the year and month the book was published.

The publication date for a book is only the year, not a month or day, and is usually identical to the copyright date.⁵

The publication date for a book consists of the year, month, week and day of publication of the book.

6. **As per the European Commission's rules of style, the italicized term *Acquis* means:**

All the achievements made by the European Union since it was established.

A corpus of laws passed by each EU country and approved by the European Union.

⁴ Bloomberg & Volpe, 168.

⁵ Turabian, 107.

- A body of law comprising the following list except the laws known as soft laws.
- A body of law comprising the following list including soft laws such as EU guidelines, policies and recommendations.**⁶
7. **According to the European Commission's rule, every acronym should be written:**
- With all letters uppercased.
- First letter capitalized and the rest lowercased.
- Only acronyms with at least five letters are fully uppercased.
- Acronyms with five letters or less are fully uppercased and acronyms with six letters or more are normally written with an initial capital followed by a lower case.**⁷
8. **Only one of the following is the correct usage of subject and verb:**
- Evelyn and me were spoilt by Uncle Wahab.
- The kids and myself went to the city center to shop for the week.
- Louis and I joined the kids at the birthday party.**⁸
- Me and my kids attended the birthday party.

⁶ The European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 2011. Accessed September 7, 2019. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/xitMjHAGfJ>, 52.

⁷ *Ibid.* 27.

⁸ EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 12, 2019), 23.

9. **Only one of the following is an accepted British usage:**

- Dear Dr Liam Fox :
- Dear Mrs. and Mr. Brown,
- Dear Mr. Brown :
- Dear Prof Smith,⁹**

10. **The direction taken by a research approach is provided by the research tradition or genre adopted by the researcher, and the different qualitative research traditions or genres promote specific strategies for data analysis. Bloomberg and Volpe reported six of those qualitative traditions. Identify one of the lists below which better represents those traditions:**

- Hermeneutics, grounded theory, ethnography, phenomenology, case study, narrative research.¹⁰**
- Grounded theory, conservatism, inductivism, hermeneutics, case study, ethnography.
- Descriptive research, positivism, ethnography, grounded theory, narrative research, case study.
- Grounded theory, cognitive anthropology, symbolic interactionism, ecological psychology, holistic ethnography, and case study.

⁹ EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 12, 2019), 35

¹⁰ Bloomberg & Volpe, 10.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.